

THE NOMINAL CLAUSES OF ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The Nominal Clauses function as like the noun phrasesⁱⁱ. This means that a nominal clause has **subject, object, complement** or **prepositional complement** etc. The nominal groups are things "*we usually add some information about it which shows how we experience or perceive the thing it is important to remember language is not reality itself, but only the way we see reality, the way we experience it*".ⁱⁱⁱ We can usually test the **nominal clause** by seeing whether we can replace the clause with it or something, e.g.

He thinks you will be surprised.	(He thinks something.)
That she got better was a miracle. ^{iv}	(Finite nominal clause – subject)
I heard that you were there.	(Finite nominal clause – subject)
I wanted you to know.	(Non-finite nominal clause – object)
He likes playing rugby.	(Non-finite nominal clause – object)

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1. Introduction

The nominal clause^v in the sentence of the Albanian and English can have different structure but sometimes (some forms) have same meaning e.g.

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ⁱⁱ Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, The Noun Phrases, Anglisticum Journal, <http://www.anglisticum.mk/index.php/Anglisticum/article/viewFile/580/647>

ⁱⁱⁱ Angela Downing & Philip Locke, A university English grammar, London, 2002, p.407.

^{iv} Graeme Kennedy. (2003). Structure and Meaning in English a Guide for Teacher. Great Britain, p. 270.

^v Shkelqim Millaku, The Noun Phrases, Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia. ISSN (print): 1857-8179. ISSN (online): 1857-8187, <http://anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1254>

He thinks you will be surprised.	(He thinks something.)
Ai mendoi të ju sjellë juve befasi.	(Ai mendoi diçka.)

Among the various types of nominal expressions in English there are two of particular importance, each roughly of propositional form. Thus, corresponding to the sentence (a) we have the gerundive nominal of (b) and the derived nominals of (c):

- a. John is eager to please.
John has refused the offer.
John criticized the book.

- b. John's^{vi} being eager to please.
John's refusing the offer.
John's criticizing the book.

- c. John's eagerness to please
John's refusal of the book.
John's criticism of the book.

Many differences have been noted between these two or three types of nominalization. The most striking differences have to do with the productivity of the process in question, the generality of the relation between the nominal and the associated proposition, and the internal structure of the nominal phrase.^{vii}

2. The nominal clause (function as a noun phrase)

The nominal clauses, functioning like noun or noun phrases, are very frequent (in Albanian and English) and can occur wherever nouns can occur as **subject, object or complement**, etc. We have some models of the nominal clause: **nominal clause as subject**^{viii}, **nominal clause as object**^{ix}, **nominal clause as complement**, **nominal clause as prepositional complement** etc.

^{vi} Shkelqim Millaku, The Contrast of the Gender between Albanian and English Language, SSRN, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3041938

^{vii} Noam Chomsky. (1972). Studies on semantics in generative grammar. Paris, p. 16.

^{viii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Noun Phrases, Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia. ISSN (print): 1857-8179. ISSN (online): 1857-8187, <http://anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1254>

^{ix} Shkelqim Millaku, The Genitive, Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia. ISSN (print): 1857-8179. ISSN (online): 1857-8187. <http://anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1218>

2.1 The Nominal Clause as Subject

In Albanian and English this type has the same function of noun phrases (noun) as the subject e.g.

A e kam kaluar testin apo jo nuk ka shumë rëndësi.
Nuk ka shumë rëndësi **a e kam kaluar testin, apo jo.**

Whether I pass the test or not does not matter very much.
It does not matter very much **whether I pass the test or not.**

2.2 The Nominal Clause^x as Object

In both of languages this type has the same function of noun phrases (noun) as the direct or indirect object e.g.

Unë **vërtetë** nuk e di **se a duhet neve makina e re.**
I don't know **whether we really need a new car.**

2.3 The Nominal Clause as Complement

This type is more complex than the simple sentence for example:

Për çka po brengosen shokët në **qoftë se do të qëndrojnë këtu ose do shkojnë diku.**
What our friends worry about is **whether to stay here or move elsewhere.**

2.4 Nominal Clause as Prepositional Complement

This raises the question as whether we should abandon the plan.

2.4.1 Nominal Clause with /that/ e.g.

That she is still alive is a consolation.

2.4.2 The Nominative Absolute is Almost a Clause

It consists of a noun phrase with a partial predicate:

He smoked briefly, his eyes following a pattern of concrete blocks in the school building^{.xi}

In Albanian and English, we observe a contrast between these phenomena. The function of the noun phrases has different structure. The most central type of determiner

^x Shkelqim Millaku, The Noun Phrases, Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia. ISSN (print): 1857-8179. ISSN (online): 1857-8187, <http://anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1254>

^{xi} Virginia Tufte. (1971). Grammar as Style, London, p. 50.

is that to which traditionally the name is used with article (definite article in Albanian^{xii} **-u, -a, -i** or in English **/the/** and indefinite article **/një/** in English **a, an**) e.g.

Mbretëresh(ë)-a. The Queen.
Poet-i. The poet.
Mik-u. The friend (s).
Një libër A book.
Një kompjuter. A computer.

Both of languages with this contrast in syntactic structure can make with noun the **subject, direct object, indirect object** and **predicate** etc.

2.5 More than One Independent Clause

In both of languages the subject usually comes before the verb and it can be noun, personal pronoun, etc. The noun can change and make the subject with personal pronoun. It is the same for Albanian and English.

Teuta/John reads a book. **She/ He** reads a book.
African literature in **Europe language** is the results of the colonialist intervention.^{xiii}
Robert Allen Warrior disagrees.
Ata shkuan në shkollë, sepse **mësuesi** kishte vendosur t'i tregonte notat.
The students study. **They** study.

The head of subject parameter in NP in English and Albanian has the genitive subject as:

John's book.
Libri i Jonit^{xiv}.

Finally, the patient-object may take the pre-nominal genitive position, with the transitive subject-agent again optionally expressed as agent –of - passive as in^{xv}:

- a. The city's description. (by the enemy) – Përshkrimi i qytetit.
- b. Teuta's knowledge. Njohurit e Teutës.

^{xii} Shkelqim Millaku, The Contrast of the Gender between Albanian and English Language, SSRN, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3041938

^{xiii} Christa Jansohn. (2002). Companion to the new literatures in English. Berlin, p. 49.

^{xiv} Shkelqim Millaku, The Genitive, Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia. ISSN (print): 1857-8179. ISSN (online): 1857-8187. <http://anglisticum.org.mk/index.php/IJLLIS/article/view/1218>

^{xv} T. Givon. (1993). English grammar I. Philadelphia, p. 291.

- c. His admission into the Bar. (by the governing Board)

Like we observe, in these examples we have a different structure between Albanian and English. In Albanian we have the first object and after the subject, but in English it is different or opposite the first is subject and after object. The subject that is expressed with the noun phrases

As a conclusion in Albanian and English this phenomenon is present, but it has some different of structure e.g.

In Albanian:

Kjo tokë është me interes për të investuar^{xvi}.

Dy burra ngritën fjalën për t'u bashkuar.

Plaku erdhi.

In English:

Our country will ultimately be directly confronted with China.

The man who just left needs help.

Shelia and **Susan** are sisters.

The old man comes.

English language has noun phrase **the old man** (article + adjective + noun) but in Albanian has the noun phrase **plaku** (just noun).

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^{xvi} Shkelqim Millaku, 2016, The Noun Phrases, Anglisticum Journal,
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